

Functionalization of anthracene by strategic utilization of the Diels–Alder reaction and the ring-closing metathesis[†]

Sambasivarao Kotha* and Milind Meshram

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Powai, Mumbai-400 076, India

E-mail : srk@chem.iitb.ac.in Fax : 91-22-2572-3480, 2576-7152

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Abstract : Herein, we present a new strategy based on the Diels–Alder (DA) reaction and ring-closing metathesis (RCM) sequence to generate the 9,10-bridged anthracene derivative such as **6**.

Keywords : Anthracene, Diels–Alder reaction, ring-closing metathesis, Grignard reaction, C–C bond cleavage.

Introduction

Anthracene **1** is a useful synthon to design alizarin dyes. Attempts to modify anthracene system led to an interesting chemistry¹. To expand the “building block” approach² to polycyclics and unusual amino acid (AAA) derivatives³ we have shown that, 9,10-dibromoanthracene is a useful starting material. In this regard, Suzuki–Miyaura cross-coupling reaction⁴ is found to be a useful tool to expand the chemical space of anthracene derivatives⁵. With a similar aim, we envisioned a new strategy based on the Diels–Alder (DA)⁶ reaction and ring-closing metathesis (RCM)⁷ sequence to generate the 9,10-bridged anthracene derivative such as **6**. For this purpose the dione **3** was identified as a key building block (Fig. 1).

Results and discussion

Our journey towards the preparation of the key building block **3**⁸ started with the DA reaction of anthracene **1**. In this connection, anthracene **1** was treated with vinylene carbonate **7**^{9c} in *o*-dichlorobenzene at 170 °C to give the DA adduct **2** in 75% yield⁹. Further, treatment of **2** with 4 *N* aq. NaOH in 1,4-dioxane furnished the diol **8** in quantitative yield. Later, **8** was subjected to oxidation with 2-iodoxybenzoic acid (IBX) in DMSO conditions, but the desired dione **3** was not realized. Then, the diol **8** was subjected to modified Swern oxidation protocol^{8a} to give the desired dione **3** in quantitative yield (Scheme 1).

Next, the dione **3** was subjected to an indium-mediated allylation¹⁰. In this context, the dione **3** was treated

Fig. 1. Retrosynthetic strategy to 9,10-bridged anthracene derivative **6**.

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Scheme 1. Preparation of diketone 3 from anthracene 1.

with indium powder in presence of the THF : H₂O (4 : 1) mixture at room temperature to furnish the monoallylated product 9 in 76% yield. Further, the monoallylated product was treated with the allyl Grignard reagent 10 in diethyl ether at -10 °C to afford the desired diallyl diol 4 in 100% yield. Subsequently, 4 was subjected to RCM^{7,10} with the aid of the Grubbs first generation (G-I) catalyst in dry CH₂Cl₂ at 50 °C for 4 h to give the cyclized product 5 in 76% yield as a white crystalline solid. Later, 5 was subjected to hydrogenation in the presence of Pd/C (10 mol%) at 1 atmospheric pressure to deliver the hydrogenated product 11 in 99% yield. Further, treatment of the diol 11 with lead tetraacetate in dry CH₂Cl₂ gave the dione 6 in 96% yield as a white solid. Formation of the dione 6 was confirmed by ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral data and further supported by the HRMS data (Scheme 2).

Next, to realize an aromatization reaction, the compound 6 was subjected to dehydrogenation sequence. In this regard, treatment of the dione 6 with DDQ or MnO₂ or IBX or Pd/C under different reaction conditions did not deliver the desired product 12. But in the some cases, the anthraquinone 13 was isolated as a minor product (Scheme 3). Formation of the anthraquinone was confirmed by ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopic techniques and further supported by thin layer chromatography (TLC) techniques.

The dione 6 was found to be air- and moisture-sensitive and it was converting slowly into anthraquinone in presence of air. Therefore, the dione 6 was subjected to LiAlH₄ reduction in dry THF to afford the diol 14 in 69% yield as a white solid which was confirmed by NMR technique and further supported by mass spectral data.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of 1,6-diketo[6](9,10)dihydroanthracenophane 6.

Scheme 3. Attempts to aromatization of the compound 6 and 14.

To realize the aromatization, the diol **14** was reacted with DDQ in refluxing toluene for 2 days but did not give the desired **15** (Scheme 3). Although the starting material was consumed, we could not isolate the required compound and the reaction mixture decomposed during the silica gel column chromatography.

Conclusion

We have designed a new route to 9,10-bridged anthracene derivative via the DA reaction and RCM sequence. Dehydrogenation step leading to [6](9,10)-anthracenophane derivatives was not successful.

Experimental

Preparation of diketone (**3**)^{8a} :

Trifluoroacetic anhydride (TFAA) (20.4 mL) was added dropwise to a stirring solution of dry DMSO (11.6 mL) in CH₂Cl₂ (120 mL) kept at -78 °C under N₂. The resulting mixture was stirred for 15 min. Later, to it was added very slowly, the solution of diol **8** (804 mg, 3.37 mmol) in DMSO (11.6 mL) and CH₂Cl₂ (50 mL). The resulting mixture was stirred for 1.5 h, followed by dropwise addition of NEt₃ (24 mL) and the stirring was continued for 1.5 h at -78 °C under N₂. The reaction mixture was warmed to room temperature. Then, the bright yellow solution was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (2 × 50 mL), organic layer was washed with water (2 × 50 mL) and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Evaporation of the or-

ganic layer at reduced pressure gave the crude product which was further purified by silica gel column chromatography. Elution of the column with CH₂Cl₂ afforded the pure compound **3** (790 mg, 100%) as bright yellow crystals; *R*_f 0.64 (silica gel, 20% EtOAc-petroleum ether); m.p. 170–172 °C; IR (neat) : 2990, 1733, 1574, 1050, 747 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.50 (4H, dd, *J*₁ 3.3, *J*₂ 3.2 Hz, Ar*H*), 7.40 (4H, dd, *J*₁, *J*₂ 3.2 Hz, Ar*H*), 5.00 (2H, s, bridge-head *CH*); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 183.9 (C=O), 134.9, 129.5, 126.5, 60.1.

Synthesis of monoallylated product (**9**) :

To a solution of diketone **3** (60 mg, 0.25 mmol) in a mixture of THF : H₂O (15 mL, 4 : 1) was added indium powder (77 mg, 2.7 equiv.) and the resulting reaction mixture was stirred vigorously, then was added allyl bromide (123 mg, 4 equiv.) and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 h, during which the reaction mixture turned into milky solution. Later, saturated solution of NaHSO₄ (5 mL) was added and then extracted with CHCl₃ (2 × 30 mL). The organic layer was washed with water (2 × 30 mL), dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Evaporation of the organic layer at reduced pressure gave the crude product. Further, it was purified by silica gel column chromatography. Elution of the column with 20% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether afforded the monoallylated product **9** (54 mg, 76%) as a white solid; *R*_f 0.55 (silica gel, 20% EtOAc-petroleum

ether); m.p. 127–129 °C; IR (neat) : 3053, 2985, 1731, 1466, 1043, 896, 739 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.45 (1H, dd, J_1 1.2, J_2 1.1 Hz, ArH), 7.40 (1H, d, J 1.6 Hz, ArH), 7.37–7.34 (2H, m, ArH), 7.28–7.19 (4H, m, ArH), 6.04–5.93 (1H, m, CH), 5.26 (1H, d, J 10.1 Hz, CH), 5.07 (1H, dd, J_1 , J_2 1.0 Hz, CH), 4.81 (1H, s, bridge-head CH), 4.49 (1H, s, bridge-head, CH), 2.30 and 2.27 (1H, ddt, J_1 , J_2 1.5 Hz and J_1 , 1.4, J_2 1.5 Hz, CH), 2.21 (1H, s, OH), 1.73 (1H, dd, J_1 , J_2 9.0 Hz, CH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 205.6 (C=O), 139.7, 136.3, 136.1, 131.7, 128.0, 127.8, 127.5, 126.5, 125.9, 125.5, 125.3, 120.0, 72.4, 60.9, 53.7, 41.3; HRMS (Q-ToF MS ES^+) : m/z : (M+Na) $^+$ calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{Na}$: 299.1048; found : 299.1050.

Synthesis of diallylated product (4) :

To a solution of monoallylated product **9** (60 mg, 0.21 mmol) in diethyl ether (15 mL) was added allyl magnesium bromide **10** (157 mg, 5 equiv.) at -10 °C under N_2 , the resulting mixture was stirred for 2 h and then quenched with saturated solution of NH_4Cl and extracted with diethyl ether (2×15 mL). The organic layer was washed with water (2×15 mL) and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Evaporation of the organic layer at reduced pressure gave the crude product. Further purification by silica gel column chromatography (20% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether) gave the diallyl compound **4** (69 mg, 100%) as white crystals; R_f 0.57 (silica gel, 20% EtOAc-petroleum ether); m.p. 136–138 °C; IR (neat) : 3426, 3076, 2978, 1265, 738 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.32 (2H, dd, J_1 3.2, J_2 3.1 Hz, ArH), 7.28 (2H, dd, J_1 3.3, J_2 4.2 Hz, ArH), 7.17 (2H, dd, J_1 , J_2 3.2 Hz, ArH), 7.14 (2H, dd, J_1 , J_2 3.2 Hz, ArH), 6.20–6.10 (2H, m, CH), 5.30 (2H, dd, J_1 , J_2 1.5 Hz, CH), 5.13 (2H, dd, J_1 0.9, J_2 8.8 Hz, CH), 4.39 (2H, s, bridge-head CH), 2.46 (2H, s, OH \times 2), 2.37 and 2.35 (2H, ddt, J_1 1.5, J_2 1.6 Hz, CH), 1.78 (2H, dd, J_1 , J_2 8.9 Hz, CH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 140.3, 139.9, 134.5, 126.7, 126.5, 126.3, 125.4, 119.1, 76.7, 54.2, 41.5; HRMS (Q-ToF MS ES^+) : m/z : (M+Na) $^+$ calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2\text{Na}$: 341.1517; found : 341.1523.

Synthesis of the RCM product (5) :

To a solution of diallylated product **4** (69 mg, 0.21 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (15 mL) was added Grubbs first

generation catalyst (10 mol%) under N_2 and the resulting mixture was heated at 50 °C for 4 h. Evaporation of the solvent gave the crude product which was purified by silica gel column chromatography. Elution of the column with 30% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether afforded the pure compound **5** as white crystals (47.1 mg, 76%); R_f 0.40 (silica gel, 20% EtOAc-petroleum ether); m.p. 240–242 °C; IR (neat) : 3054, 2978, 1559, 1362, 1061, 892, 739 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.36 (2H, dd, J_1 3.3, J_2 3.2 Hz, ArH), 7.29 (2H, dd, J_1 3.3, J_2 3.2 Hz, ArH), 7.18 (2H, dd, J_1 , J_2 3.2 Hz, ArH), 7.14 (2H, dd, J_1 , J_2 3.2 Hz, ArH), 5.85–5.83 (2H, m, CH), 4.15 (2H, s, bridge-head CH), 2.39 (1H, dd, J_1 2.7, J_2 2.9 Hz, CH), 2.36 (1H, dd, J_1 2.8, J_2 2.7 Hz, CH), 2.31 (2H, s, OH \times 2), 1.81 (2H, d, J 4.5 Hz, CH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 140.8, 140.3, 127.8, 126.9, 126.6, 126.3, 125.5, 78.1, 56.9, 37.0; HRMS (Q-ToF MS ES^+) : m/z : (M+Na) $^+$ calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{Na}$: 313.1204; found : 313.1206.

Hydrogenation of the RCM product (5) :

To a solution of RCM product **5** (33 mg, 0.11 mmol) in absolute ethanol was added Pd/C (1.22 mg, 10 mol%) under 1 atmospheric pressure of H_2 and the resulting reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 4 h. At the conclusion of reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction mixture was filtered through celite-pad. Evaporation of the solvent gave the crude product which was further purified by silica gel column chromatography. Elution of the column with 30% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether furnished the hydrogenated compound **11** as a white crystalline compound (33 mg, 99%); R_f 0.57 (silica gel, 20% EtOAc-petroleum ether); m.p. 252–254 °C; IR (neat) : 2940, 2862, 1577, 1418, 1003, 750 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.35 (2H, dd, J_1 , J_2 3.2 Hz, ArH), 7.27 (2H, dd, J_1 3.2, J_2 1.8, Hz, ArH), 7.19 (2H, dd, J_1 3.1, J_2 3.2, Hz, ArH), 7.13 (2H, dd, J_1 3.2, J_2 3.3 Hz, ArH), 4.10 (2H, s, bridge-head CH), 2.34 (2H, bs, OH \times 2), 1.65–1.55 (4H, m, CH_2), 1.46–1.40 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.13–1.06 (2H, m, CH_2); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 140.8, 140.0, 126.6, 126.4, 126.2, 125.5, 74.3, 57.6, 32.6, 14.6; HRMS (Q-ToF MS ES^+) : m/z : (M+Na) $^+$ calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2\text{Na}$: 315.1361; found : 315.1368.

Synthesis of diketone (6) :

To a solution of lead tetraacetate (63 mg, 1.5 equiv.) in dry CH₂Cl₂ (10 mL) was added diol **11** (27.3 mg, 0.093 mmol). The resulting reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 30 min. The organic layer was washed with water (2 × 15 mL) and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Evaporation of the organic layer at reduced pressure gave the crude product. Further purification by silica gel column chromatography (20% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether) afforded the pure product **6** as a white solid (26 mg, 96%); *R_f* 0.46 (silica gel, 10% EtOAc-petroleum ether); m.p. 120–122 °C; IR (neat) : 2923, 2851, 1642, 1262, 746 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.47 (4H, dd, *J*₁ 3.4, *J*₂ 3.5 Hz, ArH), 7.39 (4H, dd, *J*₁, *J*₂ 3.3 Hz, ArH), 4.92 (2H, s, bridge-head CH), 2.24–2.21 (4H, m, CH₂), 1.20 (4H, quint., *J* 2.6 Hz, CH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 210.9 (C=O), 133.9, 129.6, 128.2, 61.1, 39.5, 24.8; HRMS (Q-ToF MS ES⁺) : *m/z* : (M+H)⁺ calcd. for C₂₀H₁₉O₂ : 291.1385; found : 291.1389.

Reduction of dione (6) to diol (14) :

To a suspension of LiAlH₄ (21 mg, 0.55 mmol) in THF (12 mL) at 0 °C was added diketone **6** (33 mg, 0.11 mmol) under N₂ with stirring. Then, the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 h. At the conclusion of reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction mixture was diluted with water (10 mL) and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (2 × 10 mL). The organic layer was washed with water and dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and evaporated at reduced pressure to deliver the diol **14** as a white solid (23 mg, 69%); *R_f* 0.53 (silica gel, 10% EtOAc-petroleum ether); m.p. 157–159 °C; IR (neat) : 3410, 1448, 1259, 742 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.59 (2H, dd, *J*₁ 1.1, *J*₂ 1.3 Hz, ArH), 7.36–7.31 (4H, m, ArH), 7.30–7.24 (2H, m, ArH), 4.51 (2H, d, *J* 4.0 Hz, bridge-head CH), 4.27, (2H, q, *J* 6.8 Hz, OCH), 1.82 (2H, bs, OH × 2), 1.61–1.51 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.33–1.28 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.03–0.94 (2H, m, CH₂), 0.84–0.78 (2H, m, CH₂); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 137.9, 135.3, 129.7, 128.6, 127.3, 126.4, 78.6, 50.5, 29.8, 21.6; HRMS (ESI) : *m/z* : (M+Na)⁺ calcd. for C₂₀H₂₂O₂Na : 317.1512; found : 317.1521.

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